

FINITE ELEMENT MODELING OF THE CRUSHING BEHAVIOR OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY MEMBERS

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Abstract

Finite element models were developed to simulate the crushing behavior of graphite/epoxy members with different cross-sections and failure trigger mechanisms. Two different modeling approaches, namely, a single-layer approach and a multi-layer approach, were employed and results compared with experiments. The single-layer approach, by carefully calibrating the values of some of the parameters used in defining the contact/penetration behavior, predicted the initial failure peak load and the load-crosshead displacement curve but provided no insight into the failure process. On the other hand, the multi-layer approach captured the failure process and predicted the sustained crush load. Results of this study could be used to further investigate the integration of such energy absorbing members into the subfloor structure of a rotorcraft or aircraft.

1 Introduction

The subfloor structure of rotorcraft and aircraft is a critical component in protecting the occupants against sudden deceleration by dissipating energy during an impact event. Energy absorbing devices can be integrated into the subfloor structure to increase the energy absorption of this region thus improving the overall crashworthiness [1]. Composite materials are considered as possible candidates for such integrated energy absorbing devices due to their high strength-to-weight ratio and their high specific energy absorption (SEA), resulting from their characteristic failure process under compressive loading.

A two-part experimental study was conducted to investigate the energy absorption characteristics of graphite/epoxy members (IM7/8552) subjected to quasi-static axial compression. The first part of the study focused on the crushing behavior of circular tubes. Emphasis was placed on determining the optimal failure trigger mechanisms, including edge chamfers, crush-caps (forcing inward and outward

fiber splaying), and their combinations, to reduce the initial peak load and increase SEA [2]. The second part of the study focused on investigating structural members having open cross-sections that are more prevalent in the aerospace industry, including C-channels, right angles, and hat-stiffeners, with two different failure trigger mechanisms (edge chamfers and steeply triggers) [3].

Due to the high cost of conducting experimental studies of large structures, there is a need for reliable computational models capable of predicting the crushing response of composite members. There have been several attempts to develop explicit finite element models [4-9] with varying degrees of success. A single layer of shell elements was used in [4] to represent the laminate along with a user-defined contact between the loading platen and the specimen. Results showed that numerous numerical parameters needed to be determined in order to calibrate the simulation results to the experimental load-crosshead displacement data. A continuum damage mechanics model (CODAM) was used in [5] along with multiple layers of shell elements and a tiebreak contact definition to capture delamination. A “debris wedge” model formed between the delaminated surfaces of neighboring plies during the crushing process was incorporated to ensure accuracy of the simulation. While this approach can induce ply splaying in the experimentally-observed direction, it may not be generally applicable to other cases. Further, it was noted in [6], that CODAM requires extensive material characterization and a number of input parameters have to be obtained by correlating simulation with experiments. Other studies used multiple layers of shell elements with cohesive elements to model the delamination [7-9]. Pre-defined seam elements were introduced along the axial direction of circular and square tubes in [7,8] in order to simulate the propagation of axial cracks and yielded better comparison with the experimental results. Increasing Mode I and Mode II energy release rates for the cohesive interface also

yielded better correlation with experimental results [9].

The primary focus of this paper is on the finite element modeling and simulations performed to capture the crushing behavior of circular tubes and open cross-section members. The experimental work is briefly summarized first, followed by a description of finite element models and results of numerical simulations. Two different modeling approaches using LS-DYNA were employed, namely, the single-layer approach and the multi-layer approach..

2 Summary of Experimental Work

Specimens were fabricated using Hexcel IM7/8552 Graphite/Epoxy pre-preg. All specimens were 101.6 mm long and the open cross-section specimens were fabricated with the same cross-sectional area. Lay-up sequences and specimen dimensions are listed in

Table 1 and Fig. 1. The circular tubes were self-supporting while the open cross-section specimens were supported by a 25.4 mm thick potted base, Fig. 2, to ensure stability. All specimens included a failure trigger mechanism to initiate progressive failure during the crushing process. The circular tubes were tested with chamfers and crush-caps [2], while the open cross-sections were tested with chamfers and steeples [3].

All tests were conducted under quasi-static axial compression conditions. The tests were carried out on an Instron Testing Machine Model 1127. Loading was applied under stroke controlled mode at a displacement rate of 7.6 mm/min. All tests were terminated after a maximum displacement of 50.8 mm, providing sufficient crush data from which the amount of energy absorbed could be calculated. A summary of the experimental results that are relevant to the development of the finite element models is provided in the following two sections.

2.1 Circular Tubes

The results showed that the chamfer was very effective at reducing the initial peak load, while the inward-splaying crush-cap was most effective at increasing the sustained crush load and SEA. Further, combining an edge chamfered tube with an inward-splaying crush-cap (“combined” trigger) yielded the highest SEA with a low initial crush load. Fig. 3 shows the average load-crosshead displacement curve of the tube with the chamfer and

the combined failure trigger mechanisms. Further data are provided in [2].

2.2 Open Cross-sections

The results from this part of the study indicated that the steeple trigger is more effective than the chamfer trigger at reducing the initial crush load. The angle and hat cross-sections showed similarly high SEA’s for both failure trigger mechanisms. The C-channel specimens resulted in the lowest SEA’s in both cases. Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 show the average load-crosshead displacement curve of the open cross-section specimens with the chamfer and steeple triggers, respectively. Further data are provided in [3].

3 Single-layer Modeling Approach

3.1 Model Setup

The single-layer modeling approach used in [4] was adopted for this study. A single layer of shell elements was used to represent the laminate in the models. An element size of 1.27 x 1.27 mm was used which resulted in each model having approximately 5,500 elements. Individual plies were modeled using through-the-thickness integration points, with one integration point per ply in the thickness direction. Each integration point was assigned a ply thickness and an orientation corresponding to the stacking sequence shown in Table 1. The 45° chamfer was approximately modeled by reducing the number of plies in the first row of elements to three plies, Fig. 6, with the height of the first row being the same as that of the chamfer. The steeple trigger was modeled by making two 15° cuts to the top of the model, Fig. 6, to accurately represent the actual specimen.

3.2 Material Model

Material model 54 (MAT54) in LS-DYNA was used to simulate the crushing behavior of the specimens. MAT54 is a progressive failure model that uses the Chang-Chang failure criterion [10] to determine failure of each ply (associated with an integration point). This model allows the user to create a local material coordinate system to specify the orientation of each ply. There are 21 parameters in MAT54 that need to be specified; 15 of which are physical and six are numerical parameters [10]. Of the 15 physical parameters, 10 parameters represent material properties that were obtained from [11]. The remaining five physical parameters are tensile and compressive failure strains in the fiber and

matrix directions, respectively, and the shear failure strain. The six numerical parameters were either estimated or set to their default values, depending on the behavior required of the material model. An extensive parametric study was conducted to determine the optimal values of the unknown parameters.

3.3 Boundary Conditions and Contact Definitions

A fixed boundary condition was assigned to the nodes along the flat edge of all finite element models. Only one contact definition, between the loading platen and the chamfer/steep end of the specimen, was needed for the single-layer models. The contact definition used to model this interaction was *contact rigid nodes to rigid body*, following the approach outlined in [4]. The advantage of using this type of contact definition is that it distributes the contact force over multiple rows of elements, thus preventing the load from dropping to zero after the deletion of each row of elements. This is accomplished by allowing the nodes of the tube to penetrate into the platen by a specified distance, Fig. 7. As the nodes penetrate, they are pushed back by forces calculated based on a user specified load-penetration curve. The initial load-penetration curve used in this contact definition was estimated from the compressive failure load and cross-sectional area of the element, which was continuously “fine-tuned” as the simulation proceeded. Fig. 8 shows the final load-penetration curve used.

3.4 Simulation Results

3.4.1 Circular Tubes

As mentioned in the previous section, there are five physical and six numerical parameters in MAT54 whose values need to be determined numerically. An extensive parametric study was performed to investigate the effect of these parameters on the simulation results. It was determined that parameter DFAILC (fiber compression failure strain) had the greatest effect on the value of initial peak crush load while parameter SOFT (crash-front element softening parameter) had the greatest effect on the value of sustained crush load, which determined the value of SEA. By adjusting these two parameters it was possible to obtain simulation results that agreed very well with the experimental results. Fig. 9 shows the comparison between the simulation results of a chamfered tube with the experimental load-crosshead displacement behavior. The SEA obtained from the simulation (129 kJ/kg) compared well with the experimental SEA (127 kJ/kg).

While the single-layer approach yielded excellent agreement with experimental results in terms of load-crosshead displacement curve and SEA, it could not replicate the deformation and failure processes of the composite structure, such as matrix splitting, delamination, etc. Further, this approach could not be used to capture the effect of the crush-cap due to the unrealistic contact definition used.

3.4.2 Open Cross-sections

With open cross-section specimens an attempt was made to determine a common set of values for the 11 numerical parameters that could be used to simulate the crushing behavior of the different cross-sections and failure trigger mechanisms. An extensive parametric study was conducted to find the required parameters using the C-channel specimen. Similar to the case of the circular tubes, by adjusting the values of the DFAILC and SOFT parameters it was possible to obtain simulation results that correlated well with the experimental data for the C-channel with a chamfer trigger, Fig. 10. The same parameter values were then used in the chamfer trigger models of the angle and hat stiffeners. It was found that, by varying the value of the SOFT parameter it was possible to match the crush load and SEA values from simulations to the experimental results. However, the initial peak loads were not predicted accurately, indicating that the DFAILC parameter needed to be modified as well, **Error! Reference source not found.** In other words, a different set of SOFT and DFAILC values is needed for each cross section in order to accurately predict both the peak load and SEA.

A similar parametric study was performed for the C-channel with a steep trigger. However, it was not possible to establish a similar correlation due to the lack of a chamfered row of elements to take advantage of the SOFT parameter, Fig. 11. This model was very sensitive to minor changes to the DFAIL and SOFT parameters, often resulting in unstable collapse. When the C-channel stiffener parameters were applied to the hat and angle stiffener models, poor correlation was obtained, Table 3. That is, the predictions of the peak load and SEA for each cross-section strongly depend on the proper selection of the material parameters, i.e., fiber compression failure strain and crash-front element softening parameter. This should be expected since different failure processes are associated with

different cross-sections and different geometries of the failure triggers.

4 Multi-layer Modeling Approach

4.1 Model Setup

In the multi-layer approach the laminate was divided into multiple layers of shell elements that were tied together using a tiebreak contact definition. To improve computational efficiency, multiple plies were grouped together into one shell elements layer. The circular tubes consisted of nine plies that were divided into three shell element layers representing three plies each. The open cross-sections consisted of ten plies that were divided into five shell element layers representing two plies each. As in the single layer model, each ply was represented by a single integration point through the thickness of the shell element layer. An element size of 1.27 x 1.27 mm was used for the flat sections in the models (web and flanges). For curved sections (tubes and corners of open cross-section models) a refined element size of 0.635 x 0.635 mm was used for a more accurate simulation of the damage progression in these regions. This resulted in the tube model having approximately 77,000 elements and the open cross-section models having approximately 55,000 elements. The 45° chamfer was modeled by staggering the length of each shell layer such that the inner layer's first row of elements represented the start of the chamfer, and the outer layer represented the end of the chamfer. The steeple trigger was modeled by making two 15° cuts to the top of the model.

4.2 Material Model

Material model MAT54 was used to represent each ply, as was the case in the single-layer approach. In this case, however, the only MAT54 parameter that needed to be determined was DFAILM, which is the failure strain in the matrix direction. Adjusting the value of DFAILM enabled matrix splitting to occur, as observed in the experiments. A parametric study was performed to determine the optimal value of DFAILM for the C-channel with a chamfer trigger model. It was found that the corner elements required a larger value of DFAILM than the elements on the flat sections to accurately represent crack formation and propagation along the corners. It should be noted that the thicknesses of the corners in the test specimens were not consistent with the flat sections. In the finite element models the same thickness was used throughout the entire cross-

section. This warranted using a separate DFAILM value for the corner elements.

Once an optimal set of DFAILM values was determined for the C-channel with a chamfer trigger, it was applied to the other five models (C-channel with a steeple trigger, angle and hat stiffeners with chamfer and steeple triggers).

4.3 Boundary Conditions and Contact Definitions

All boundary conditions used in the models were accurate representations of the experimental setup. The circular tubes did not require any boundary conditions as they were placed standing upright between the loading platen and the base of the Instron machine. The open cross-sections required the nodes along the flat end of the models to be fixed in all degrees of freedom to simulate the potted base used for support.

The interaction between the loading platen and the specimens was modeled using a surface to surface contact definition (*contact automatic surface to surface*).

As mentioned earlier, the shell layers were tied together using a tiebreak contact definition (*contact one way surface to surface tiebreak*) with option 8 [10]. This tiebreak formulation allowed for simulating delamination at the interface between each shell element layer. Damage initiates when the stress reaches a failure criterion based on the normal and shear interlaminar strengths [10], defined as

$$\left(\frac{|\sigma_n|}{NFLS}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{|\sigma_s|}{SFLS}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (1)$$

where σ_n and σ_s are the normal and shear stresses acting on the interface, while *NFLS* and *SFLS* are the normal and shear failure stresses of the tie, respectively. The stress is then scaled as a linear function of the separation distance.

The critical distance to failure (*CCRIT*) can be calculated from the energy released due to the failure of the interface,

$$E_{tie} = \frac{1}{2} \times S \times CCRIT \quad (2)$$

where

$$S = \sqrt{\max(\sigma_n, 0)^2 + |\sigma_s|^2} \quad (3)$$

at the initiation of damage. For pure Mode II delamination $\sigma_n = 0$ and $\sigma_s = SFLS$, Equations (2) and (3) can be rewritten as

$$CCRIT = \frac{2 \times E_{tie}}{SFLS} \quad (4)$$

where E_{tie} is equal to the Mode II critical energy release rate, G_{IIC} , obtained from [12] for IM7/8552. Hence, with values for $NFLS$ and $SFLS$ known, all required input parameters for this tiebreak formulation are available. It is noted that the simulation of progressive delamination is mesh size dependent and typically requires a very fine mesh. To improve the computational efficiency, the methodologies discussed in [13] were adopted. While the methodologies proposed in [13] were intended for use with cohesive zone models, they can be applied to the tiebreak formulation used here as well since the tiebreaks follow a traction-separation law similar to that used in cohesive zone formulations. The proposed solution involves lowering the interfacial strengths whilst keeping the fracture toughness constant in order to adapt the length of the cohesive zone for a given mesh size. The required interfacial strength $\bar{\tau}^0$ can be calculated as

$$\bar{\tau}^0 = \sqrt{\frac{9\pi EG_c}{32N_e^0 l_e}} \quad (5)$$

where E is the transverse modulus E_2 for orthotropic materials, G_c is the fracture energy release rate, N_e^0 is the desired number of elements in cohesive zone, and l_e is the mesh size in the direction of delamination. The minimum number of elements needed in the cohesive zone has not been well established. Various studies have used anywhere from two elements to 10 elements in the cohesive zone [13]. In this study, it was determined that five elements were sufficient to simulate the propagation of delamination. Hence, with $N_e^0 = 5$, equation (5) was used to solve for the new $NFLS$ and $SFLS$ values. The new $SFLS$ was substituted into equation (4) to calculate the $CCRIT$ value.

As mentioned earlier, in order to improve computational efficiency, each shell layer represents multiple plies (three for the tube and two for the open cross-sections). Hence, the tiebreak contact was required only between each shell layer, rather than each ply. However, in reality delamination could occur along any, if not all, ply interfaces as the specimen is crushed. Therefore, in order to account for the energy from these unaccounted for delamination interfaces, $CCRIT$ was scaled by the ratio of the number of ply interfaces n_{delam} to the number of tiebreak interfaces n_{tie} , defined as

$$CCRIT' = CCRIT \times \frac{n_{delam}}{n_{tie}} \quad (6)$$

The values calculated using equations (4), (5) and (6) were used to simulate the various combinations of cross-sections and failure trigger mechanisms studied.

4.4 Simulation of the Crushing Process

4.4.1 Circular Tubes

Simulations of the circular tubes with a chamfer trigger and a combined trigger mechanism were performed. Results show that the approach described above provided a good depiction of the failure process (Fig. 12). In the chamfered tube case, the simulation predicted that the outer layer of shell elements (three plies) splayed outwards, while the other two shell element layers splayed inwards. In the experiment, however, only two plies splayed outwards while seven splayed inwards. The simulation would not be able to capture this level of detail due to the grouping of three plies per shell layer. In the combined trigger case, both the simulation and experiment showed that all plies splayed inwards, as expected.

When comparing the simulation to the experimental load-crosshead displacement curve of the chamfered tube, it was seen that the simulation displayed three high initial peaks, Fig. 13, corresponding to the crushing of the three shell element layers in the chamfered region. Since the plies were not modeled individually, it was not possible to obtain a realistic representation of a 45° chamfer. However, it was determined that by applying an SAE 300 Hz filter to these data, a smoother initial peak load was obtained (Fig. 13) that compared very well with the experimental results, Fig. 14. It should be noted that this filter did not affect the sustained crush load and overall SEA. These values correlated very well with the experimental results regardless of the filter applied, Fig. 15 and Fig. 16. Similar results were obtained with the simulation of the circular tube with the combined trigger mechanism, Fig. 15 and Fig. 16.

4.4.2 Open Cross-sections

Simulations of the open cross-section specimen with a chamfer and steep failure trigger mechanisms were performed as well. The results showed, Fig. 17, that the simulation was capable of accurately depicting the failure process of the test specimen in terms of crack propagation at the corners, delamination and the splaying direction of individual plies.

A representative comparison of the load-crosshead displacement curves for the C-Channel having a

chamfer trigger is shown in Fig. 18. As with the circular tube simulations, the approximate modeling of the chamfer also resulted in high initial fluctuations and required filtering to obtain more reasonable results. Since each shell element layer represented only two plies in this case (as opposed to three in the circular tubes) an SAE 600 Hz filter was sufficient to obtain good correlation with the experimental data. A comparison of the simulation results obtained for all chamfer trigger cases is shown in Fig. 19 (peak load and crush load) and Fig. 20 (SEA). Good correlation was observed for the SEA of the C-channel and hat specimens; however, the simulation of the angle cross-section yielded an SEA which was higher by 11% as compared with the experiments.

A comparison of representative load-crosshead displacement curves for the hat stiffener with a steeple trigger is shown in Fig. 21. For the steeple trigger simulations, no filtering of the results was required since the steeple was modeled accurately. A comparison of the simulation results obtained for all steeple trigger cases is shown in Fig. 22 (peak load and crush load) and Fig. 23 (SEA). Good correlation was observed for the SEA of all specimens; however, the angle simulation under predicted the peak load by 34%.

5 Conclusions

In this study, finite element models were developed using LS-DYNA to simulate the crushing behavior of composite stanchions. Two approaches were employed to model the crushing process, namely, a single-layer approach and a multi-layer approach. The single-layer approach was able to accurately replicate the load-crosshead displacement curve of the C-channel with a chamfer trigger. This approach involved performing an extensive parametric study to obtain the values of certain parameters required by material model 54 (MAT54) to correctly fit the simulation results to the experimental load-crosshead displacement data. It was determined that two parameters, DFAILC and SOFT, play a key role in predicting the initial peak load and sustained crush load, respectively. An attempt was made to find a common set of parameters that could be used across the different cross-sections; however, each cross-section requires a separate DFAILC and SOFT definition. This method proved to be even more unsuccessful when applied to specimens with a steeple trigger mechanism due to the lack of the chamfer row of elements to effectively use the

SOFT parameters. These models were mostly unstable and it was not possible to find a common set of parameters to use between the different cross-sections.

For the multi-layer approach, it was determined that DFAILM was the only parameter that needed to be adjusted in order to obtain good correlation with the experimental results. A parametric study was performed to determine an optimal set of input parameters for the C-channel with a chamfer trigger. Further, an energy based approach was employed to determine the critical distance to failure for the tiebreak contact definition. These parameters were then used across the remaining case studies. Overall, the results obtained were highly satisfactory with the approach being able to accurately replicate the crushing process observed in the experiments. In most cases, the load-crosshead displacement curve and SEA was well predicted.

References

- [1] D. Ludin and M. Renninger, "The Development of a Floor Former Concept Incorporating Energy Absorbing Composite Tubes," *Proceedings of the 65th American Helicopter Society Annual Forum*, Grapevine, TX, May 27-29, 2009.
- [2] D. Siromani, G. Henderson, D. Mikita, K. Mirarchi, R. Park, J. Smolko, J. Awerbuch and T.-M. Tan "Experimental and numerical crashworthiness investigation into the energy absorption mechanisms of axially loaded CFRP tubes". *Proceedings of the American Society for Composites 26th Technical Conference*, Montreal, QC, Vol. 3, pp 2681-2700, 2011.
- [3] D. Siromani, B. Cheng, M. DeLuca, D. Donegan, P. Giberson, C. Mucerino, J. Awerbuch and T.-M. Tan, "An Experimental and numerical study on the energy absorption mechanisms of axially loaded graphite/epoxy members with various cross-sections". *Proceedings of the American Society for Composites 27th Technical Conference*, Arlington, TX, 2012.
- [4] P. Feraboli, B. Wade, F. Deleo, M. Rassaian, M. Higgins and A. Byar "LS-DYNA MAT54 modeling of the axial crushing of a composite tape sinusoidal specimen". *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 42, No. 11, pp 1809-1825, 2011.
- [5] C. McGregor, R. Vaziri, X. Xiao "Finite element modeling of the progressive crushing of braided composite tubes under axial impact". *Impact Engineering*, Vol. 37, pp 662-672, 2010.
- [6] X. Xiao "Modeling energy absorption with a damage mechanics based composite material model". *Composite Materials*, Vol. 43, No. 5, pp 427-444, 2009.

- [7] S. Palanivelu, W. Paepegem, J. Degrieck, D. Kakogiannis, J. Ackeren and D. Hemelrijck “Parametric study of crushing parameters and failure patterns of pultruded composite tubes using cohesive elements and seam, Part I: Central delamination and triggering modeling”. *Polymer Testing*, Vol. 29, pp 729-741, 2010.
- [8] S. Palanivelu, W. Paepegem, J. Degrieck, D. Kakogiannis, J. Ackeren and D. Hemelrijck “Parametric study of crushing parameters and failure patterns of pultruded composite tubes using cohesive elements and seam, Part II: Multiple delaminations and initial geometric imperfections”. *Polymer Testing*, Vol. 29, pp 803-814, 2010.
- [9] M. Joosten, S. Dutton, D. Kelly and R. Thomson “Experimental and numerical investigation of the crushing response of an open section composite energy absorbing element”. *Composite Structures*, Vol. 93, pp 682-689, 2011.
- [10] LS-DYNA Keyword user’s manual, Version 971, Livermore Software Technology Corporation, Livermore, USA; 2006.
- [11] P. Camanho, P. Maimi and C. Davila “Prediction of size effects in notched laminates using continuum damage mechanics”. *Composite Science and Technology*, Vol. 67, pp 2715-2727, 2007.
- [12] P. Hansen and R. Martin “DCB, 4ENF and MMB delamination characterization of S2/8552 and IM7/8552”. Final Technical Report US Army N68171-98-M-5177. 1999.
- [13] A. Turona, C. Davila, P. Camanho and J. Costa “An engineering solution for mesh size effects in the simulation of delamination using cohesive zone models”. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*. Vol. 74, pp 1665-1682, 2007.

Table 1: Specimen configuration

Geometry	Lay-up	Length in (mm)	Cross-sectional area in ² (mm ²)	Wall thickness in (mm)	Failure trigger mechanism
Circular Tube	[-15/+15/0 ₃ /-15/+15/0 ₂]	4 (101.6)	0.22 (142)	0.054 (1.37)	Chamfer/Crush-cap
C-channel	[0 ₂ /+45/-45/0 ₂ /-45/+45/0 ₂]	4 (101.6)	0.28 (180)	0.06 (1.52)	Chamfer/Steeple
Hat Stiffener	[0 ₂ /+45/-45/0 ₂ /-45/+45/0 ₂]	4 (101.6)	0.28 (180)	0.06 (1.52)	Chamfer/Steeple
Angle Stiffener	[0 ₂ /+45/-45/0 ₂ /+45/-45/0 ₂] _s	4 (101.6)	0.28 (180)	0.12 (3.04)	Chamfer/Steeple

Table 2: Correlation between the experimental and simulation results for each cross-section with a chamfer trigger

Specimen	Peak Load [Error %]	Crush Load [Error %]	SEA [Error %]
C-Channel	3.9%	6.4%	7.2%
Angle Stiffener	20.1%	5.1%	5.4%
Hat Stiffener	20.5%	3.1%	1.4%

Table 3: Correlation between the experimental and simulation results for each cross-section with a steeple trigger

Specimen	Peak Load [Error %]	Crush Load [Error %]	SEA [Error %]
C-Channel	21.9%	17.8%	0.4%
Angle Stiffener	66.7%	58.1%	64.0%
Hat Stiffener	30.3%	24.6%	33.3%

Fig. 1: Test specimens cross-sectional dimension (all dimensions in mm)

Fig. 2: Test specimens

Fig. 3: A comparison of experimental load-crosshead displacement curves of tubes having a chamfer trigger and tubes having a combined trigger.

Fig. 4: A comparison of experimental load-crosshead displacement curves of C-Channel, Angle and Hat stiffeners having a chamfer trigger.

Fig. 5: A comparison of experimental load-crosshead displacement curves of C-Channel, Angle and Hat stiffeners having a steeple trigger.

Fig. 6: Single-layer finite element models of (a) circular tube with a chamfer; and (b) C-channel with a steeple.

Fig. 7: Penetration of the platen by tube elements according to the load-penetration curve in the contact definition.

Fig. 8: Final load-penetration curve for the contact definition used in single-layer model.

Fig. 9: Single-layer simulation vs. experimental load-crosshead displacement curve for the circular tubes having a chamfer trigger.

Fig. 10: Single-layer simulation vs. experimental load-crosshead displacement curve for the C-channels having a chamfer trigger.

Fig. 11: Single-layer simulation vs. experimental load-crosshead displacement curve for the C-channels having a steeple trigger.

Fig. 12: A comparison of the final deformation of the experimental and simulation circular tube having (a) a chamfer failure trigger; and (b) a combined failure trigger mechanism (chamfer and crush-cap).

Fig. 13: Effect of filtering on multi-layer simulation load-crosshead displacement curve for the circular tubes having a chamfer failure trigger.

Fig. 14: Multi-layer simulation vs. experimental load-crosshead displacement curve for the circular tubes having a chamfer failure trigger.

Fig. 15: Multi-layer simulation vs. experimental peak load and crush load comparison for the circular tubes having a chamfer failure trigger and a combined failure trigger.

Fig. 16: Multi-layer simulation vs. experimental SEA comparison for the circular tubes having a chamfer failure trigger and a combined failure trigger.

Fig. 17: A comparison of the experiment vs. simulation final deformation of the hat stiffener with a steep failure triggering mechanism.

Fig. 18: Multi-layer simulation vs. experimental load-crosshead displacement curve for the C-Channel having a chamfer failure trigger.

Fig. 19: Multi-layer simulation vs. experimental peak load and crush load comparison for the open cross-sections having a chamfer failure trigger.

Fig. 20: Multi-layer simulation vs. experimental SEA comparison for the open cross-sections having a chamfer failure trigger.

Fig. 21: Multi-layer simulation vs. experimental load-crosshead displacement curve for the Hat stiffener having a steeple failure trigger.

Fig. 22: Multi-layer simulation vs. experimental peak load and crush load comparison for the open cross-sections having a steeple failure trigger.

Fig. 23: Multi-layer simulation vs. experimental SEA comparison for the open cross-sections having a steeple failure trigger.